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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Yangi O'zbekiston sharoitida ayollar ijtimoiy faolligini oshirishda psixologik motivatsiya va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish strategiyalari	26
<i>Xuseynova Abira Amanovna</i>	
Pragmalinguodidactic Principles in Teaching English for Philologist Students and their Application in Intercultural Communication.....	31
<i>Arzieva Bibi-Sanem Aynazarovna</i>	
Metakognitiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan biologiya o'quv materiallarini loyihalash, joriy etish va samaradorligini baholash.....	35
<i>Abdurasulova Gulrux Habibullayevna</i>	
Oligofreniya holatida neyropsixologik tashxislar qo'llanilishining umumiy masalalari	40
<i>Akramov Dostonbek Ikromjon o'g'li, Xojaliyeva Sarvinoz Elyorjon qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarida kreativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida ...	44
<i>Asatova Dildora Aslamovna</i>	
Ingliz tili o'qish ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirishda autentik manbalarning roli.....	49
<i>Bekmuratova Nargiza Arislanbayevna</i>	
Insuldan keyingi nutqni tiklashda logopedik reabilitatsiya va nevrologik muolajalar integratsiyasi	52
<i>Boltaboyeva Xurshida Sharofiddinovna</i>	
The Concept of Symbols in Linguoculturology	56
<i>Hamraqulova Gulandom Sodiq qizi</i>	
Buyuk ipak yo'li xalqlari o'rtasidagi pedagogik va madaniy aloqalarning vujudga kelishi.....	59
<i>Mirxalilova Nargiza Akbarovna</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni bolalarni nutqini o'stirishga bo'lgan kasbiy-pedagogik tayyorgarligini o'stirish	63
<i>Mitaliboyeva Dildora</i>	
Koxlear implantli bolalarning eshituv–nutqiy faolligini oshirishda differensial yondashuv asosida korreksion-pedagogik ish	66
<i>Nartayeva Shahoza Yulchibayevna</i>	
Fasilitatsion yondashuv asosida kichik maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda adaptiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishning psixologik-pedagogik mexanizmlari.....	71
<i>Normatova Nilufar Komilovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda disgrafiyasi bo'lgan o'quvchilarda yozish kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari (XIX–XXI asrlarda).....	76
<i>Qaxxorova Saidaxon, Mamarajabova Zulfiya</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar va onlayn platformalar orqali olimpiya ta'limini rivojlantirish: yoshlar orasida axloqiy va jismoniy madaniyatni oshirish	80
<i>Qodirov Jurabek Mamatsimonovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida sun'iy intellekt bilim va savodxonligini rivojlantiradigan innovatsion jismoniy-interaktiv o'yinlar: pedagogik model.....	83
<i>Quvonova Nodirabegim Shavkat qizi</i>	
“Sab' ai sayyor” asarida qo'llangan onomastik birliklar haqida mulohazalar	87
<i>Gadayev Oybek Yaxshiboyevich, Ravshanova Sharbatoy Rahmatilla qizi</i>	
Ijtimoiy tarmoq shifokorlarining masofaviy konsultatsiyalari shaxs psixikasi va salomatligiga ta'siri	91
<i>Askarova Nargiza Abdivaliyevna, Ravshanova Zarnigor Daminovna</i>	
Talabalar ilmiy dunyoqarashini rivojlantirishda innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari va interfaol metodlardan foydalanish.....	95
<i>Satvoldiyev Faxriddin Akbarali o'g'li</i>	
Innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari orqali pedagoglarning kreativligini rivojlantirish	99
<i>Saydullayeva Gulasal Umidjon qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar motorikasini rivojlantirishning standart modeli	102
<i>Sirojiddinova Xamidaxon Xasanboy qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning shaxslararo munosabat kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	106
<i>Turg'unova Gulnoza Muhammadjonovna, Xodjiyeva Mahliyo</i>	

Shaxsdagi mehnat motivatsiyasi samaradorligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiluvchi korrelyatsion bog'liqliklar tahlili	109
Xusanov Samariddin Maxmadaminovich	
Auditoriyadan tashqari musiqiy mashg'ulotlarni art-terapiya yordamida tashkil etish asoslari	112
Yarashev Jo'rabek To'rayevich	
Формирование творческого мышления школьников на уроках музыки	117
Габдульманова Ильнура Минисламовна	
Теоретико-методологические основы коллаборативного обучения, кооперативных подходов и интерактивных педагогических методов	119
Жураева Мафтуна Бахтиёр кизи	
Педагогическое колесо как инструмент формирования цифровой компетентности будущих педагогов дошкольного образования.....	124
Уразова М. Б., Усманова У. Б.	
Особенности гражданского воспитания обучающихся в системе “школа–махалла” в Узбекистане ..	130
Хайдаров Шавкат Шамсиддин угли	
Педагогические условия формирования языковой грамотности у учащихся с тяжелыми нарушениями речи.....	135
Юсупова Зулайхо Бахром кизи	
Valeologik tarbiyada o'yin texnologiyalarining ahamiyati.....	139
Berkinova Charos Islomovna	
O'quvchilarda faol fuqarolik kompetensiyasi tushunchasi, mazmuni va shakllanishi	142
Buvorayeva Gulruh Shoikrom qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda STEAM yondashuvi asosida o'qitishning didaktik imkoniyatlari	145
Cho'tboyeva Munisxon Eshpo'lat qizi	
Tabiatga muhabbat: maktabgacha ta'limda milliy qadriyatlar va o'yinlar orqali ekologik tarbiya	150
Ergasheva Umriniso Komilovna	
Zamonaviy ta'lim – talabalar ijtimoiy intellektini shakllantirish omilidir.....	153
Ermatova Gulnoz Pirimovna	
O'zbekistonning eng yangi tarixi fanini o'qitishda pedagogik texnologiyaning o'rni	156
Gazibekova Feruza Hakimovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining raqamli texnologiyalar muhitida tanqidiy va mustaqil fikrlashini rivojlantirish metodikasi	159
Haydarova Feruza Haydar qizi	
Talabalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy fazilatlar va sifatlarni shakllantirish mexanizmi.....	162
Jumanazarova Dilnoza Umurzaqovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning kasbga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini shakllantirishda interfaol metodlarni qo'llash texnologiyasi.....	165
Jumayeva Malika Aliyevna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarda kasbiy-nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish.....	168
Lutfetdinova Ra'no Xusnetdinovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda matematik rivojlanishga zamonaviy yondashuvlar va jahon tajribalari ..	172
Masharipova Barno Erkin qizi, Adilbayeva Dilnoza Adilbay qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida til o'yinlari texnologiyalarining nazariy asoslari.....	175
Masharipova Dilfuza Muxammatjon qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachisi pedagogik faoliyatining o'ziga xosligi	178
Muhammadiyeva Feruza Turakulovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini og'zaki va yozma nutqini rivojlantirishda aksiologik yondashuvdan foydalanish metodikasi.....	181
Muhiddinova Munira Xayrullayevna	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida matematika fanini o'qitishda raqamli transformatsiya vositalaridan foydalanishning metodik paradigmasi	184
Narzullayeva Sevara Omonovna	
O'qituvchining muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	187
Nizamova Nodira Paxritdinovna	
Integrativ yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarning nutqiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning mazmuniy izohlanishi	191
Oysha Qurbonova, Nodira Abduraimova	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda Finlandiya tajribasi	195
Nodira Sherboyeva	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Kutubxonachi kutubxona-axborot xizmati jarayonining yetakchi ishtirokchisi sifatida 198 O'ktam Nosirov Pedagogik ta'lim transformatsiyasida talabalarning tadqiqotchilik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi..... 204 Rustamova Shoxista Omonjonovna Globallashuv sharoitida axborot-psixologik xavfsizlikni shakllantirish masalalari..... 208 Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li Talabalarga ingliz tilini o'qitishning zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalari 212 Sa'dullayeva Rushana Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida o'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish 215 Saidova Dilbar Erkinovna Pedagog xodimlarda tolerantlik namoyon bo'lishining determinantlari..... 218 Sattorova Maxliyo Dilmurod qizi Kreativ metodlar orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kreativ tafakkur va fikrlashni rivojlantirish 223 Sultonboyeva Baxriniso Ilhomjon qizi Artpedagogika texnologiyalaridan foydalanib maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda dialogik nutqni rivojlantirish metodikasi 226 Xolmatova Fotima Baxtiyor qizi Boshlang'ich ta'limda yashil kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish yo'nalishlari..... 229 Yaqubova Shoira Tog'aymuratovna Emotsional intellektni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari..... 233 Yarmatov Raxmboy Baxramovich Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'quv veb-saytlari orqali til kompetentligini rivojlantirish 239 Zokirova Sohiba Muxtoraliyevna, Muxammadjonova Diyorabonu Muzaffarjon qizi Языковые изменения в русском языке XXI века: исследование новых слов, сленга, интернет- коммуникации, влияния англицизмов и глобализации на современный русский язык 242 Марупова Дилфуза Давроновна Oliy ta'limda talabalarning ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyatining maqsad va vazifalari 247 F. R. Xosilova Boshlang'ich ta'lim texnologiya darslarida o'quvchilarni tabiiy materiallar bilan ishlashga o'rgatish 251 Kambarov Nodirjon Sattarovich, Nasirjanova Feruzaxon Alixon qizi Boshlang'ich ta'limda STEAM yondashuvining qo'llanilishi va uning samaradorligi..... 256 Abdulazizova Yulduz Abdujabbor qizi Tabiiy fanlarni o'qitishda STEAM yondashuvi asosida kreativlikni rivojlantirish metodikasi 259 Abdullayeva Dilrabo Fayzulla qizi Umumta'lim maktablarida o'quvchilarda shaxs ma'naviy qiyofasini shakllantirishning zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalari..... 262 Aliyeva Zuxra Tursunboyevna Yosh avlodni madaniy-tarixiy yondashuv asosida tarbiyalashda madaniy-ma'rifiy muassasalarning o'rni.. 265 Aripov Shokirjon Olimovich Ta'limda yangi texnologiya: 4K modeli va uni amalga oshirish yo'llari..... 268 Avliyoqulova Nasiba Choriyevna Badiiy-tarixiy materiallarni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiyalashning metodologik asoslari..... 272 Baratov Baxtiyorjon Qodirovich Bolaning maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotiga moslashishida o'yinning roli..... 275 Barno Masharipova Erkin qizi, Zuhrobova Mahliyo Abdulatif qizi Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish savodxonligi darslarida integrativ yondoshuvdan foydalanish texnologiyasi 278 Ernazarova Laylo Abdusaitovna, Saidahmadova Gulrux Farrux qizi Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda metarefleksiv fikrlashni rivojlantirishning psixologik-pedagogik asoslari 284 Ismailova Nilufar Isroildjanovna Semantic and Cross-Cultural Features of Food-Based Idioms in Karakalpak and English Languages..... 289 Jiemuratova Gulistan Koshkinbaevna Filolog talabalarida mustaqil fikrlash va qaror qabul qilishni rivojlantirishda metakognitiv yondashuvlarning didaktik mexanizmlari..... 292 Jo'rayeva Dilnoza Ro'zimat qizi Rivojlantiruvchi sohalar kompetensiyalariga integratsion yondashuv asosida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalash texnologiyasini rivojlantirish 296 Jo'rayeva Zilola Sayfiddin qizi
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Psixologlar kasbiy komponentlarini rivojlantirishda matematik usullardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	302
<i>Kuziyeva Dilnura Dilmurotovna</i>	
O'zbekiston metodik maktabida sotsiolingvistik kompetensiyani shakllantirish bo'yicha olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlar tahlili	306
<i>Madaminova Gulzira Gulamkadirovna</i>	
Maxsus pedagogika fanlarini o'qitishning nazariy-metodik asoslari	313
<i>Maqsudova Nodira Alijonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda metakognitiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishda ertakterapiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish metodikasi	317
<i>Muxiddinova Dilfuza Sherdor qizi</i>	
Nutq madaniyatini shakllantirishda o'qituvchi nutqining roli.....	320
<i>N. Q. Olimova</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida matematika fanini o'qitishda raqamli transformatsiya vositalaridan foydalanishning metodik paradigmasi	323
<i>Narzullayeva Sevara Omonovna</i>	
O'quvchilarda ekologik madaniyatni shakllantirish metodikasi	326
<i>Normirzayeva Maftunaxon Ilyosjon qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tadqiqot faoliyatini rivojlantirishda intensiv ta'lim texnologiyalarining metodik asoslari.....	329
<i>Olloqulova Farzona Umedillayevna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi giperaktiv bolalar bilan ishlashda pedagogik kompetentligini oshirish metodikasi.....	332
<i>Raimqulova Sojida Abdusaid qizi</i>	
Talabalarning tadqiqotchilik kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari	335
<i>Rustamova Shoxista Omonjonovna</i>	
Inklyuziv ta'limni tashkil etishning xorijiy pedagogik amaliyotdagi modellari	339
<i>Sultonova Zarina Uchqun qizi</i>	
Xalq pedagogikasida ertaklarning tarbiyaviy va ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ahamiyati: ma'naviy begonlashuvga qarshi tarbiyaviy omil sifatida.....	343
<i>To'xtasinova Farida Davlatali qizi</i>	
B1 darajadagi talabalar uchun xorijiy tilni o'qitishda audiovizual texnologiyalar yordamida ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishning metodik asoslari	347
<i>Toshpulatova Shaxsanam Xolmurodovna</i>	
Kontekstli ta'lim va uning boshlang'ich ta'lim matematikasidagi ahamiyati haqida	350
<i>Umarova Nigora Alisherovna</i>	
Oiladagi psixologik muhitning o'spirinlarda to'liqsizlik kompleksi shakllanishiga ta'siri	353
<i>Xalmuratova Dilorom Abdikarimovna</i>	
Ta'limda faktcheking: misinformatsiya va dizinformatsiyaga qarshi kurashishning pedagogik asoslari	356
<i>Xidirova Maftuna Ithom qizi</i>	
Maktab o'quvchilarini falsafiy va dunyoqarashga tayyorlash omillari	362
<i>Xo'shboqova Farida Komiljon qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida nutq faoliyatini rivojlantirishning lingokognitiv asoslari	370
<i>Xusanova Gulruxsor To'lqin qizi, Aliyeva Muhlis Baxodir qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyasini oshirish	374
<i>Zokirova Sohobaxon Muxtaraliyevna, Erkinova Nazokatxon Anvarjon qizi</i>	
Эффективность занятий кроссфитом в повышении уровня общей физической подготовленности слушателей института повышения квалификации МВД Республики Узбекистан	377
<i>Албеков Шокир Адилбекович</i>	
Роль торговых и кочевых маршрутов в формировании лингвокультурных заимствований между Хорезмом и Южной Сибирью.....	381
<i>Сатымова Светлана Сатымовна</i>	
Использование искусственного интеллекта в обучении русскому языку как иностранному: проблемы и решения.....	385
<i>Ташева Дилором Салимовна</i>	
Проблемы использования коммуникативного метода в преподавании русского языка студентам	389
<i>Тоджибоева Наргиза Джумабоевна</i>	

Maktab–oila–mahalla hamkorligining qizlar ijtimoiy faolligini oshirishga ta'siri	393
<i>Abdurazoqova Marg'uba Muxammad qizi</i>	
Ta'lim tizimida musiqiy madaniyatni takomillashtirishning metodologik imkoniyatlari.....	397
<i>Asqarova Xurshida A'zamjon qizi</i>	
Maktab biologiya kursini o'qitishda dars va darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarning o'zaro bog'liqligi asosida metodologik savodxonlikni shakllantirish.....	404
<i>Azimov Bekjon Ibrohimjon o'g'li</i>	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida iqtidorli talabalar bilan ishlash samaradorligini ta'minlash usullari.....	407
<i>Delov To'liqin Erkinovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarni badiiy asarlarni janriy xususiyatlariga ko'ra izohli o'qishga o'rgatish	410
<i>Gulmira Abdullayeva</i>	
O'zbekiston bokschilarining dunyo reytingida yetakchi o'rinlarni egallashining asosiy omillari	413
<i>Insapov Ismoil Tuychaliyevich</i>	
Improving Learners' Engagement Through Game-Based Techniques in Language Education	416
<i>Ismailova Ma'rifat Bakhrambek kizi</i>	
STEAM yondashuvi boshlang'ich ta'limda ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning zamonaviy kaliti sifatida	421
<i>Jo'rayeva Nasiba Komil qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarni milliy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiyalashning ijtimoiylashuvi	426
<i>Jo'rayeva Sayyora Vahobjon qizi</i>	
O'smirlarda xarakter aksentuatsiyasining o'ziga bo'lgan ishonch rivojlanishiga ta'sirining psixologik xususiyatlari	429
<i>Jurayev Xaydarjon Odilboyevich</i>	
O'spirinlarda agressiv xulqqa ta'sir qiluvchi omillar	433
<i>Konratbayeva Ayjamal Bazarbayevna</i>	
Rus va o'zbek tillarida chorvachilik terminlarining qiyosiy tahlili.....	436
<i>Kurbanova Guzal Abduraximovna</i>	
Texnologiya darslarida murakkab mexanizmlarni o'qitishning zamonaviy usullari	441
<i>Mamadaliyev Furqat Xolmamatovich</i>	
Umumta'lim maktab o'qituvchilarining sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish madaniyatini shakllantirish usullari	446
<i>Mamatova Fazilat Ixtiyorovna, Xolmirzayeva Zebo Ravshan qizi</i>	
Nutqda badiiy tasviriy vositalardan foydalanish yo'llari.....	450
<i>Murodova Farangis G'anisherovna</i>	
Kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarning yozma savodxonligini oshirish yo'llari.....	454
<i>N. Abduvaliyeva, M. Odinajonova</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar shaxslararo munosabatini korreksiyalashda ertak terapiyasidan foydalanish	458
<i>Nig'matova Nodirabegim Lutfillo qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida o'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	463
<i>O'rinova Ro'zigul Jumanazar qizi</i>	
Voleybol o'yinida blok qo'yish texnikasini o'rgatishda yangi pedagogik yondashuvlar	467
<i>Qambarov Kozimjon</i>	
Texnik yo'nalishda tahsil olayotgan talabalarga ingliz tilini o'qitishning yangi texnologiyalari	472
<i>Babayeva Gulnozaxon Latibjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim sifatini oshirishda pedagog malakasining roli	481
<i>Davlatova Dildora Nuriddinovna</i>	
Talabalarda sog'lom turmush tarzini rivojlantirishning pedagogik tamoyillari	485
<i>Davronov Nurzod Ismoilovich</i>	
Eshitishda nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar: toifalari va tasniflash mezonlari	490
<i>Djurayeva Sohiba Barat qizi</i>	
Blum taksonomiyasiga asoslanib boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining og'zaki va yozma nutqini rivojlantirish usullari.....	495
<i>Husenova Aziza Sharipovna</i>	
Tabiiy fan darslari jarayonida o'quvchilarda loyihaviy ishlarni tashkil etish ko'nikmasini shakllantirish	498
<i>Matniyazova Diyora Jumanazarovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limni modernizatsiya qilishning asosiy yo'nalishlari: innovatsion taraqqiyot, metodik yangiliklar va istiqbollari	501
<i>Nazarova Mohigul Akmalovna, Asatova Mashhura Asomiddin qizi</i>	

Kasbiy pedagogikani shakllantirish va rivojlantirish masalalari	506
<i>Sanaqulov Xamroqul Rizaqulovich</i>	
O'qituvchining shaxsiy fazilatlari va suggestiv kompetentligining o'zaro bog'liqligi	513
<i>Shermatova Manzura Ikromjanovna</i>	
Tez qalamchizgilarda innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llash tajribasi	518
<i>Suyunov Navro'z Alisher o'g'li</i>	
Kognitiv tilshunoslik asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqini rivojlantirish	523
<i>Teshabiyev Dilmurod Raxmadjonovich, Madazimova Muxlisa Abdurashid qizi</i>	
Kombinatorik masalalar asosida ijodiy topshiriqlarni tuzish va ularning o'quvchilarga ta'siri	526
<i>Toshboyeva Saida Rahmonberdiyevna, Yusupova Latofat Abduqodir qizi</i>	
Linguodidactic Foundations for Enhancing Professional Competence in Practice-Oriented Language Education	530
<i>Uktamova Navruza Botir qizi</i>	
Audiovizual usul qo'llanilganda o'quvchilarning til ko'nikmalaridagi o'zgarishlarni baholash	535
<i>Umarov Aziz Avazovich</i>	
Ona tili – ART texnologiya va kreativlik fanida so'z san'atining omili sifatida	540
<i>X. Sanaqulov, Sh. Nurmatova</i>	
Etnopedagogik yondashuvning boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijtimoiylashuv jarayoniga ta'siri	543
<i>Xamroqulova Xilola Qosimjon qizi</i>	
Ajdodlarimiz o'g'itlari asosida o'quvchi-yoshlarda axloqiy sifatlarni shakllantirish texnologiyasi	547
<i>Xatamova Nilufar Xaydarovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ o'qish madaniyatini rivojlantirishda generativ sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining didaktik imkoniyatlari	550
<i>Xayitova Firuza Abdullayevna</i>	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda maktabgacha ta'limning mazmuni va tarixiy taraqqiyoti	554
<i>Yoziyeva Umida Lutfullayevna</i>	
O'quv vaziyatlarini loyihalash orqali talabalar o'quv faolligini oshirish	558
<i>Zakirova Dilfuza Sayidolimovna</i>	
O'quvchilar orasida jismoniy faollikni oshirish uchun yangi ilmiy yondashuvlar	561
<i>Zaynobidinov Dilshodbek Qobilovich</i>	
Активные методы обучения как коммуникационная основа современного урока	566
<i>Ахмедова Мукаддас Ходиматовна</i>	
Инклюзия как путь к равным возможностям: развитие системы образования Узбекистана	570
<i>Баротова Шохсанам Бахтиёр кизи, Мауш Ребия Джамshedовна, Мурадова Дилфуза Махмудовна</i>	
“Qurilish konstruksiyalari” fanini o'qitishda kasbiy-amaliy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish	576
<i>No'manova Soxiba Ergashboyevna</i>	
Креативный педагогический подход в музыкально-теоретических и практических занятиях по искусству макома	582
<i>Нурматова Фируза Муминовна</i>	
Система упражнений по методике обучения средствам речевой выразительности узбекского языка	587
<i>Фаттахова Д. А.</i>	
Oliy ta'limda kompetensiyaga asoslangan o'qitish modellari	592
<i>Ernazarov Alisher Ergashevich, Chinqulova Gulmehra</i>	
The Concept of Symbols in Linguoculturology	598
<i>Hamraqulova Gulandom Sodiq qizi</i>	
Raqamli o'yinlarga (mobile games) qaramlikning kognitiv samaradorlikka salbiy ta'siri	601
<i>Turamov Muhammadzohid Rustamjon o'g'li</i>	
OTM talabalarini vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalash asosida ilmiy tadqiqot ishlariga yo'naltirishning zamonaviy metodlari	605
<i>Sobirov Zahridin Sadriddinovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda o'quvchilarda kiriyativlikni rivojlantirish	609
<i>Qo'chqarov Mirzavali Qo'zibayevich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari tarbiyalanuvchilarining axloqiy tarbiyasini shakllantirish	613
<i>Yaqubova Dinora Bahodirovna</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida AR (Augmented Reality) texnologiyalarining qo'llanilishi	617
<i>Abdumo'minov Burxonjon Sunnatillo o'g'li</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	The Role of Psychological Support in the Formation of Students' Socio-Emotional Competence in Preschool Education 622 <i>Kamol'dinova Diyora Jaloliddin qizi</i>
	Raqamli ta'lim muhitida o'quvchilarning mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish metodikasi 626 <i>Xudoynazarova Moxira Xakimovna</i>
	Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida talabalarda tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini metodlar orqali rivojlantirish 629 <i>Ro'zmetov Ravshan Sharipbayevich</i>
	Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda muloqot madaniyatini tarbiyalash 633 <i>Uljayeva Sevara Abdirazzoqovna</i>
	Kompetensiyaviy yondashuvga asoslangan zamonaviy darsliklar tuzilishi va mazmuni 638 <i>Po'latova Marjona Inomjon qizi</i>
	STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasini maktabgacha ta'limida qo'llash bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar 643 <i>Saidova Nigora Olimovna, Pirmatova Zaynabxon Elmurod qizi</i>
	Raqamli texnologiyalar vositasida bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning pedagogik muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantirish 646 <i>Ergasheva Sunbula Baxtiyor qizi</i>
	O'quvchilarda ijtimoiy tarmoqlarga qaramlikning shakllanishi va uning dolzarb muammolari 650 <i>Gaparova Mastona Safaraliyevna</i>
	Adabiyot darslarini o'qitishda 5E modelidan foydalanish 654 <i>Abdiraupova Zarnigor Abdinabi qizi</i>
	Oliy ta'limda kompetensiyaga asoslangan o'qitish modellari 657 <i>Ernazarov Alisher Ergashovich, Chinqulova Gulmehra</i>
	Traditional Techniques and Modern Approaches in the Production of National Costumes 665 <i>Jabborova Dilshoda Xolmamat qizi</i>
	Pedagogik platformalar va kognitiv-didaktik yondashuvlar integratsiyasi yordamida talabalarning kasbiy tayyorgarlik tizimini yangi bosqichga olib chiqish 668 <i>Raxmonov Omadjon Mamasidiq o'g'li</i>
	Aqli zaif o'quvchilarda disgrafiyani bartaraf etishda assistiv texnologiyalarning ahamiyati 672 <i>Usmonov Umid Allayorovich</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tayanch hayotiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish 676 <i>Adizova Nigora Baxtiyorovna, Akbarova Sarvinoz Sadriddinovna</i>
	Tadqiqotchilik kompetentligi pedagogik muammo sifatida 681 <i>Ergashev Nozim Nabiyevich</i>
	Teaching Reading to Young Learners: Essential Principles for Primary School Teachers 684 <i>Toshtanova Maftuna Xamidjon qizi</i>
	Tarmoq qurilmalari va tizimlarini boshqarish modulini o'qitish orqali o'quvchilarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlash 687 <i>Karimova Charos Abduhalim qizi</i>
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda og'zaki nutq rivojlanishining psixolingvistik asoslari 691 <i>Musayeva Nafisa Kudratovna, Muxammadova Saodat Muzaffar qizi</i>
	"Kasbiy ma'naviyat" fani bo'lajak pedagoglarda ma'naviy-axloqiy kompetensiyalarni intensiv rivojlantirish omili 695 <i>Ismoilov Yoqubjon Quchqarboyevich</i>
	Yapon tilini o'rgatishda talabalarning gapirish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirish: tamoyillar, bosqichlar va innovatsion usullar 699 <i>Baqoyev Navro'zjon Abdullo o'g'li</i>
	Texnologik ta'lim jarayonida ixtirochilik va loyihalashtirish kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari 705 <i>Zokirova Nargiza Akbarjonovna</i>
	Bo'lajak pedagoglarda kasbiy kompetentlikni shakllantirishning psixologik asoslari 710 <i>Eshnazarova Farida Jo'raqulovna</i>
	Ta'lim islohotlari sharoitida genderni yo'naltirilgan ta'limni tashkil etishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari 714 <i>Yaxyayeva Sojida Abduraximovna</i>
	Ko'rsatish olmoshlarining vazifaviy uslublarda qo'llanilishi 718 <i>Berdiyeva Malika</i>
	Nazorat turlari orqali o'quvchilarning savodxonlik kompensatsiyasini shakllantirish 721 <i>Xoldarova Irodaxon Valijonovna, Jo'rayeva Shodiya Kenjaali qizi</i>

Zamonaviy boshlang'ich ta'limni modernizatsiya qilish sharoitida o'quvchilarda lug'atlar bilan ishlash kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	726
Buvajonova Mohiraxon Usmonali qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'limni modernizatsiya qilishning asosiy yo'nalishlari: innovatsion taraqqiyot, metodik yangiliklar va istiqbollari	731
Nazarova Mohigul Akmalovna	
Maktab va pedagogika institutlari o'rtasida amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan dual ta'lim modelini takomillashtirish: muammolar va yechimlar	736
Arabova Muxiba Bazarovna	
Помощь советского государства в подготовке кадров для арабских государств	740
Хомидова Камола	
Место Узбекистана в развитии культурной сферы Советского союза во второй половине XX века ..	744
Бекназаров Собиржон	
Toshkent xalqaro kinofestivallarining Arab davlatlari va Afrika mamlakatlari kinosan'atida tutgan o'rni	748
Sharifov Shoxjaxon To'liqinjon o'g'li	
Ekonometrika fanini o'qitishda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning nazariy asoslari va istiqbollari	752
Bobonorova Qundizxon Quralbay qizi	
O'quvchi faolligini oshirishda jadid maktablari tajribasi va faol ta'lim metodlarining integrativ qo'llanilishi ..	759
Bobonazarov Orif Abrayqulovich	
Влияние гендерной лингвистики на развитие психолингвистических исследований в Узбекистане ..	764
Мусаева Елена Казимовна	
Psixik rivojlanishni tashxislashda psixofiziologik usullardan foydalanish samaradorligi	767
Sh. L. Rahmonova	
Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida o'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	770
Saidova Dilbar Erkinovna	
Ingliz tili o'qitishda integrativ (CLIL) texnologiyasining boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun mos modellarini ishlab chiqish	773
Xakimova Xosiyat Jurayevna	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlar ta'lim tizimida talabalarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish usullari	776
Mirzayeva Faroxat Odiljonovna, Odiljonova Shoxsanam Abdug'appon qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirishda innovatsion o'yin metodlarining ahamiyati	785
Ikromov Ilxom Muxamadraximovich	
Tabiat tasvirining adabiy janrlarga ko'ra o'ziga xosliklari	790
Fozilova Mohigul Farxodovna	
Методические подходы к развитию прагматической компетентности старшеклассников на основе чтения аутентичных материалов	794
Исаматдинова Машхура Икромжон кизи	
O'zbek tilida "zahar" konseptining leksik-semantik va pragmatik xususiyatlari	799
Shokirov Sherhali Ibrohimovich, Baxramov Xabibillo Sadikovich	
Integrativ modulli o'qitish tizimi samaradorligining miqdoriy va sifat tahlili	803
Nurmanova Nazira	
Sog'lom turmush tarzi ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda STEAM ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati	807
Toshova Shaxnoza Tojidorovna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga harakatga doir masalalarni klaster metodida o'rgatish	811
Badalov Dilmurod Abdixalilovich	
Ona tili darslarida o'quv lug'atlaridan foydalanishning o'quvchilarning og'zaki nutq kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi didaktik asoslari	817
Ahmedova Adiba Ulug'bek qizi	
Philosophical Aspects and Analysis of the Regularities of the Formation of Geo-Economic Thinking	822
Ubaydullayev Islomjon Abdullayevich	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarini sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanishga tayyorlashning pedagogik asoslari	826
Xudayqulova Fazilat Bo'riyevna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	<p>Boshlang'ich ta'lim va tarbiya jarayonida o'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini shakllantirishda ommaviy axborot vositalarining (Media/Mass Communication) roli..... 831 Bo'ronova Dilrabo Ne'matullayevna</p> <p>Inkluziv maktab sharoitida kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-perseptiv tajribani shakllantirish 835 Karimova Zulfiya Abduraxmanovna</p> <p>TEACCH konsepsiyasi – autizm va kommunikativ buzilishlari bo'lgan bolalarni davolash va o'qitish dasturi..... 839 Murodova Sarvigul Raxim qizi</p> <p>Модернизация кадровой политики дошкольных учреждений через инновационные мониторинговые механизмы 843 Ким Нигора Каримовна</p> <p>Bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarining metodik kompetentligini ergonomik yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish 847 Usmonova Xafiza</p> <p>Pedagogik improvizatsiya asosida talabalar o'quv faoliyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik strategiyalari 852 Ergasheva Muhayyoxon G'anijonovna</p> <p>Talabalar orasida ilmiy-pedagogik tadqiqotlarni tashkil etish va o'tkazish 857 Nurmatova Madina Odiljon qizi, Qo'shoqova Farangiz Azizbek qizi</p> <p>O'quvchi-yoshlarni oilaga nisbatan ma'naviy-axloqiy va qadriyatli munosabatlarga tayyorlash – ijtimoiy-pedagogik zaruriyat sifatida 861 Xaydarov Oxunjon Murodjonovich</p> <p>Talabalarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda mustaqil ta'limning ilmiy-metodik ahamiyati 866 B. Normamatova</p> <p>Talabalarda pedagogik e'tiqodni shakllantirishning variativ modeli va uning asosiy komponentlari 869 Bahranova Hulkar Bahran qizi</p> <p>Konvensial yondashuv asosida talabalarni mustaqil ta'lim olish samaradorligining didaktik imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirish..... 872 Berdiyev Bahodir Ravshanovich</p> <p>Kontekstli yondashuvga asoslangan o'quv-ijodiy faoliyatning turlari 875 Botirova Zilola Nodirovna</p> <p>Raqamli texnologiyalar vositasida bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning pedagogik muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantirish..... 878 Ergasheva Sunbula Baxtiyor qizi</p> <p>Boshlang'ich sinflarida ta'lim o'quvchilarga sonlar haqida ma'lumot berish 882 Hakimova Zulfizar Umrzoq qizi</p> <p>Biologiya ta'limida elektron ta'lim (E-Learning) va aralash ta'lim (Blended Learning) texnologiyalarining samaradorligini tahlil qilish..... 886 Kozimov Akbarjon A'zamjon o'g'li</p> <p>Alisher Navoiy asarlarida ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyaga oid fikrlari tahlili..... 891 M. Ibragimova</p> <p>Integratsiyalashgan dars ta'limiy faoliyat samaradaorligini ta'minlovchi muhim omil sifatida 894 Mahmatqulova Xosiyat Bobomurod qizi</p> <p>Tarbiyalanuvchilarni xalq og'zaki ijodi namunalari asosida ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalashning mazmunini ochib berish..... 897 Murodillayeva Durdona Dilmurodovna</p> <p>Sun'iy intellekt davrida bolalar adabiyoti: raqamli qahramonlar, interaktiv ertaklar va bolaning ijodiy tafakkuri rivoji 900 Normurodova Nigora Abdusattorovna, Sharipova Iroda Rashid qizi</p> <p>Qadimgi va o'rta asr mutafakkirlarining matematika fanining shakllanishi va rivojlanishidagi o'rni 903 Quvvatova Ozoda Gulbek qizi</p> <p>Shaxs xolistik rivojlanishi – psixologik-pedagogik muammo sifatida 906 Rashidova Xurriyat Sulaymonova</p> <p>Bolalarda elementar matematik tasavvurlarni shakllantirishning psixologik-pedagogik asoslari..... 908 Ravshanova Kamola Toxirovna</p> <p>Matematikaga rivojiga ulkan hissa qo'shgan olimlar 911 To'rayeva Kamola Vosidjon qizi</p>
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Umumiy o'rta ta'limda mexanika masalalarini yechish metodikasi va o'qitish jarayonining didaktik asoslari	914
<i>Toxirova Maxfuzaxon Otaqo'ziyevna</i>	
Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachi-pedagogalarining kasbiy-axloqiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish	916
<i>Xabibullayeva Sayyoraxon Maxamadali qizi</i>	
TRIZ va kreativ pedagogika: boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy muammolarni hal qilish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	919
<i>Ortiqova Zulfiya Nurmaxammatovna, Fayzullayeva Nazokat Uchqunovna</i>	
Maktab ta'limi uchun mobil ilova yaratishda MIT APP inventor platformasidan foydalanish	922
<i>Tangirov Xurram Ergashevich, Xo'jamqulova Dilso'z Bahodir qizi</i>	
Pedagogical Methods for Improving Students' Creative Thinking as they Learn	927
<i>Akhmedov Alisher Astanovich, Yarmuhamedov Nabijon</i>	
Implementation Outcomes and Development Prospects of the Social And Legal Club in the Secondary Vocational Education System as a Tool for Delivering Social Services	932
<i>Makhmudova UgiLOY Baxtiyarovna</i>	
Educational Physics Experiments: Methods and Didactic Strategies for Developing Critical Thinking in Students	935
<i>Chakkanov Fakhriddin Xusanovich</i>	
Current Research and Suggestions on The Impact of Physical Activity on Adolescents' Mental Health	938
<i>Irgashev Shokhrukh Khasanovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida tarbiyachi shaxsiga qo'yiladigan zamonaviy pedagogik talablar	941
<i>Gaziyeva Nigora shamsiddinovna, Abdiraxmonova Nilufar Muxiddinovna</i>	
Eshituv va fonematik idrokni rivojlantirishda neyropsixologik o'yin usullari	945
<i>Lutfullayeva Sadoqat Muzaffar qizi, Axmedova Zuxra Mirzabekovna</i>	
Metodlarning turlari va nazariy asoslari	948
<i>Murodova Durdona Rayimjon qizi, Ashurova Hulkaroy Ma'rufjon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak biologiya o'qituvchilarining tizimli tafakkurini rivojlantirishda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash samaradorligini aniqlash: pedagogik tajriba-sinov natijalari va matematik-statistik tahlil	952
<i>Mustafaqulova Dildora Ismatullayevna</i>	
Raqamli texnologiya ta'limga imkoniyatmi yoki xavf?	960
<i>Otanazarova Mehriniso Abdusharif qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy sharoitlarda ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlarni olib borish uslubiyoti va unga qo'yilayotgan talablar ...	963
<i>Ortiqova Nargiza Akramovna, Suvonqulova Muxabbat Otamurot qizi</i>	
Interactive Grammar Learning Methods and their Significance for Non-Philological Education Students .	969
<i>Almatova Umida Islomovna</i>	
Berilganlar bazasi konsepsiyalarining evolyutsiyasi va zamonaviy rivojlanish bosqichlari	975
<i>Nosirova Shohista Elmurodovna</i>	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda milliy g'urur hissini shakllantirishda tarbiyachining pedagogik ahamiyati	980
<i>Kadirova Shaxnoza Xudoyberdiyevna</i>	
Autentik matnlar orqali o'quvchilarda o'qishga motivatsiya shakllantirish	987
<i>Usmonova Gulhumor Qo'ldashboy qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida "Aralash ta'lim (Blended Learning)" texnologiyasining joriy etilishi	991
<i>Sh. D. Ablakulov</i>	
Ko'paytirish amalini o'rgatishga zamonaviy yondashuv (suv vositasida)	995
<i>Ismoilov Bobur Toxirovich</i>	
WEB dasturlash fanining ahamiyati va rivojlanish tendensiyalari	1000
<i>Ovxunov Iqboljon Abdunabiyevich, Abdullayev Javohirbek Zokirjon o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarida metakognitiv kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodik xususiyatlari	1005
<i>Sattorova Go'zalxon Mamadaminovna</i>	
Reflective Technologies of Development of Sanogen Thinking in Students	1010
<i>Ismailov Murodulla Kahramonovich</i>	
Tinglab tushunish ko'nikmasini rivojlantiruvchi o'quv topshiriqlarini takomillashtirishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari	1014
<i>Avazova Farangiz Ixtiyor qizi</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Surxon adabiy maktabi: Usmon Azim va Shafolat Rahmatulla Termiziy ijodi..... 1022 <i>Xolboyeva Dilafuz Xayrulla qizi</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tanqidiy mazmundagi masalalar asosida ijodiy fikrlash kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish 1026 <i>Ahmadjonova Intizor Iqboljon qizi, Dehqonova Mahliyo Shuhrat qizi</i>
	Tarbiyalanuvchilarda miqdor va son tushunchalariga doir ta'limiy o'yin faoliyatlari jarayonida ixtiyoriy diqqatini shakllantirish..... 1030 <i>Quysinova Shahlo Nasim qizi</i>
	Alaliyali bolalar bilan logopedik ishning tizimli yondashuvi 1035 <i>Irkinova Irodaxon Temirovna</i>
	Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida o'quvchilarni eshitish va talaffuzga paralel ravishda rivojlantirish: integratsiyalashgan yondashuv 1040 <i>Raximova Mahliyo Xasanboy qizi</i>
	Gender xususiyatlarning ijtimoiy shartlangan ko'rinishlari 1043 <i>Yulduzxon Mirzaaxmedova</i>
	Oliy ta'limda muhandislik fizikasi fanini o'qitishning didaktik imkoniyatlarini takomillashtirish 1047 <i>Butayeva Nargiza Buriboyovna</i>
	Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kreativ kompetentligini integrativ yondashuv asosida shakllantirish modeli..... 1051 <i>Askarova Zilolaxon Nurmuhamadovna</i>
	Sun'iy intellekt asosida ta'limni individuallashtirishning pedagogik asoslari 1055 <i>Abdullayev Alibek Qodiraliyevich, Toxirova Muattarxon Isroil qizi</i>
	Matematik fizika tenglamalari fanini o'qitishda yuqori tartibli differensial tenglamalar bo'limining o'rni va ahamiyati 1060 <i>Murzambetova Mexriban Begdullayevna</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari tarbiyasida ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikni tashkil etish metodikasi 1064 <i>Fayziyeva Madinabonu Sohibjon qizi</i>
	O'tkir Hoshimovning realistik xarakter yaratish mahorati..... 1070 <i>Nortojiyev Muxammad</i>
	Bolalar adabiyoti asarlarini tahlil qilishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning imkoniyatlari 1073 <i>Xujamqulova Iroda Faxriddinovna</i>
	O'quv jarayoni ishtirokchilari o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabatlarning bolalarda bilish faolligini rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati 1078 <i>Achilov Obid Muzrobovich</i>
	Maktab o'quvchilarida mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish, o'tkazish va baholash metodikasi..... 1083 <i>Musayeva Gulnoza Yo'ldosh qizi</i>
	Bo'lg'usi pedagoglarda estetik kompetensiyani rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida..... 1087 <i>Bozorova O'g'iloy Komilovna</i>
	"Taskari teorema" innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyasi 1093 <i>Yandasheva Sevara Ne'matjonovna</i>
	Technologies for Forming Students' Communicative Competence Based on Interdisciplinary Integration..... 1096 <i>Umida Eshmirzayevna Mamatkulova</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida mantiqiy va ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishda elementar matematikaning o'rni 1101 <i>Djuraboyev Maqsudbek Karimbek o'g'li, Badridinov Nusratbek Xusniddin o'g'li</i>
	Zamonaviy muhandisni tayyorlash texnologiyasi – kasbiy kompetentlikni shakllantirish imperativi sifatida 1105 <i>Axmedova Aziza Shokir qizi</i>
	Yengil atletika sportchilarida yadro itqitish harakati biomexanik ko'rsatkichlarining texnik samaradorlikka ta'siri 1110 <i>Djabbarov Axror Islomovich</i>
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarining sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish kompetensiyasini shakllantirish 1114 <i>Artikova Nargiz Shuxratovna</i>
	O'quvchilarni tayanch hayotiy kompetensiyalar orqali iqtisodiy bilimlarini shakllantirish 1118 <i>Adizova Nigora Baxtiyorovna, Sayfullayeva Dilnoza Amrullayevna</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodkorlik qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda interfaol ta'lim metodlarining pedagogik samaradorligi..... 1123 <i>Ortiqova Zulfiya Nurmaxamatovna, Oripova Shaxzodaxon Otamurod qizi</i>

Integrativ yondashuv asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarni ma'naviy tarbiya faoliyatiga tayyorlashning pedagogik mexanizmlari.....	1127
Rahmatjonzoda Ahrorjon Ahmad o'g'li	
Ta'lim transformatsiyasi sharoitida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	1130
Beknazarova Muxlisa O'tkir qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlashda oila va maktab hamkorligi	1135
Mamadaliyeva Gavxarxon Asiljonovna	
Pedagogik amaliyotda pedagogik mahoratni rivojlantirishning nazariy–amaliy asoslari	1139
Yunusova Feruza Maxamadolim qizi	
O'quvchilarda milliy xarakter xususiyatlarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik aspektlari	1143
Hasanova Gulmira Hoshimjanovna	
Maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarga she'riy asarlarni o'qitishga doir ayrim metodlar (O. Matjonning "Orolga yordam" she'ri asosida).....	1147
Alxiyeva Sitora Raximqul qizi	
Sport travmalaridan keyingi reabilitatsiyada jismoniy tarbiya vositalaridan foydalanishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari	1150
Begimqulov Oltiboy Jo'rayevich	
Demografik vaziyatning mohiyati va tarkibi	1155
Bomurodov Sanjar Bekmurodovich	
Problems of Developing the Terminology System of the Uzbek Language.....	1159
Dilnoza Yuldasheva Bekmurodovna	
Tarbiya darslarida guruh va jamoaviy o'yinlar orqali muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirish	1163
Menlibayeva Azima Oralbayevna	
Raqamlashtirilgan ta'limda talabalarni tanqidiy fikrlash asosida kommunikativ kompetentligini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	1166
Nuritdinova Xurshida Narpulatovna	
Raqamli ta'lim vositalarining boshlang'ich ta'limdagi afzalliklari	1169
Sattorova Mohira	
The Importance of Teaching Physics Through Modern Educational Trends	1172
Sharofutdinov Ikboljon Usmonjon ugli	
Maktabgacha ta'lim pedagoglarining kasbiy rivojlanishida gender rollar nazariyasining amaliy ahamiyati	1176
Tolipova Noilaxon Nodir qizi	
Interfaol metodlar orqali boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirish	1183
Umida Bovanova Abdurahobovna, Bo'riboeva Navbahor Faxriddinov	
Zamonaviy ilg'or xorijiy tajribalar asosida qon aylanish tizimi mavzusini o'qitishning innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash imkoniyatlari	1186
Xaqberdiyeva Sh. T.	
Ingliz tili darslarida kreativlikni oshirishda kuzatiladigan muammolar va ularni yechishga doir pedagogik yondashuvlar.....	1190
Yusupov Lutfullo Sayitturayevich	
Informatika fanini o'qitishda qo'llaniladigan innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari ("Axborotlarni kodlash" mavzusi misolida).....	1194
Temirova Gulbahor G'ulomovna, Yusupova Nodira Nurdinovna	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'quv veb-saytlari orqali til kompetentligini rivojlantirish	1201
Zokirova Sohiba Muxtoraliyevna, Muxammadjonova Diyorabonu Muzaffarjon qizi	
Innovatsion ta'lim sharoitida "maktabgacha ta'limda menejment" fanini o'qitishning didaktik imkoniyatlari	1204
Astanakulova Manzura Buribayevna	
Milliy qadriyatlar vositasida o'quvchilarni chet tili o'rganish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	1209
Toshturdiyeva Xurshida Erkinovna, Elmurodova Dildora Erkinovna	
Talabalarda jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirishda individual yondashuvning nazariy asoslari	1212
Islomov Eldor Yusupovich	
Pedagogik jarayon subyektlarining intellektual imkoniyatlarini diagnostik o'rganish va korreksiyalash metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	1215
Sattorova Malikaxon Abdug'affor qizi	
Языковые изменения в русском языке XXI века: исследование новых слов, сленга, интернет-коммуникации, влияния англицизмов и глобализации на современный русский язык	1220
Марупова Дилфуза Давроновна	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Ta'lim jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarni mantiqiy fikrlashga o'rgatish 1226 <i>Adizova Nigora Baxtiyorovna, Bahodirova Mohinur Azamat qizi</i>
	Buxoro xonlariga pir bo'lgan Dahbediyar 1231 <i>Kandaxarov Anvarjon Xasanovich</i>
	Formativ baholash natijalaridan ta'lim sifatini yaxshilashda foydalanish 1236 <i>Mamatova Fazilat Ixtiyorovna, Jabborova Dilshoda Xolmamat qizi</i>
	Современные тенденции развития в подготовке юных волейболистов с использованием инновационных технологий 1239 <i>Имомов Сирожиддин Илхомович</i>
	Современное развитие гандбола, основы технико-тактической подготовки и методика обучения в кружках 1244 <i>Оринов Облакул Жумаевич</i>
	Теоретико-методические основы баскетбола и современные тенденции его развития 1248 <i>Ачилов Ойбек Хакимович</i>
	O'zbekistonda ekoturizmni rivojlantirishda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining qo'llanishi: holat, muammolar va rivojlanish istiqbollari 1252 <i>Berdiyev Baxtiyor Sodiqovich, Raximjonova Maxliyoxon Zokirjon qizi</i>
	Sun'iy intellekt asosida talabalarning dasturlash kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish 1257 <i>Saidov Usmon Bahron o'g'li</i>
	Современные методы устранения заикания у подростков 1260 <i>Абдухалимова Муниса Абдурашид кизи</i>
	O'quvchilarda innovatsion yondashuv orqali ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya berishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari 1264 <i>Xamidova Shaxnoza Nuraliyevna</i>
	Iqtidorli futbolchilarni tanlab olishning nazariy asoslari 1268 <i>Salayev Taxirbek Kamiljanovich, Atajanov Adilbek Yuldashevich</i>
	Sun'iy intellektning talabalarda analitik fikrlashga ta'siri 1274 <i>Abduhakimova Muslima Bahodir qizi</i>
	Raqamli interpretatsiya: vizual tahlil kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda immersiv texnologiya va kognitiv yuklanishni optimallashtirish 1277 <i>Anvarxo'jayeva Dilinur Otabek qizi</i>
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarining sun'iy intellektidan foydalanish kompetensiyasini shakllantirish 1282 <i>Artikova Nargiz Shuxratovna</i>
	Ekologik turizmning tabiatga ma'naviy-estetik munosabatni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari 1286 <i>Aymatov A. Q., Turayeva Dildora Shuhratovna</i>
	O'quvchilarda milliy tuyg'ularni shakllantirishning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari 1289 <i>Begmatova Nasiba Safarbayevna</i>
	Katta maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda duduqlanishni korreksiyalashning pedagogik texnologiyasi 1293 <i>Boxodirova Gulasalxon Ibroximovna</i>
	Jismoniy tarbiya va sog'lomlashtirish mashg'ulotlarida lotin va yunon terminlarining o'rni 1296 <i>Burxonova Guyoxon Gulomovna</i>
	Ta'lim jarayonlarida sinergetik kompetensiyalash orqali integrativ yondashuvni amalga oshirish 1300 <i>Haqberdiyev Baxtiyor Rustamovich</i>
	Montessori metodikasining tarixi, tamoyillari va ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o'qitishdagi o'ziga xos usullari 1304 <i>Jo'raqulova Gulruh Murot qizi</i>
	Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning ijtimoiy-pedagogik kompetentligini rivojlantirish holati va muammolari 1307 <i>Karimov Ravshanbek Rizomatovich</i>
	Methodology for the Integrative Development of Students' Educational and Creative Activities in Teaching Fine Arts 1312 <i>Kurbanova Shohsanam Bakhodirjon kizi</i>
	Kurash sport turining jismoniy tarbiya tizimida tutgan o'rni va uning rivojlanish omillari 1315 <i>Mamadova Feruzaxon Mirzaaxmad qizi, Akbarova Nasibaxon Abdumalik qizi</i>
	Kurash sport turining texnik-taktik rivojlanishi va uning jismoniy tarbiyadagi pedagogik ahamiyati 1319 <i>Mamadova Feruzaxon Mirzaaxmad qizi, Eminjonova Zahro Dilmurodjon qizi</i>
	Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning intellektual qobiliyatini falsafiy bilimlar asosida rivojlantirish shakllari 1323 <i>Mamatqulova Shaxnoza O'ktam qizi</i>

Using Debate, Role-Play, and Drama as Tools for Developing Oral Skills in English	1326
Menglibekov Reynazar Mukhammetkarim-uli	
Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarida supervayzerlik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishning psixologik determinantlari	1329
Mirzayeva Muhayyo Ruziyevna	
Methodology for Developing Patriotic Education in Students Through Ideas of National Heroism	1334
Nomanova Ma'rifat Abdillayevna	
Shaxsda kasbiy tafakkur namoyon bo'lishining psixologik mexanizmlari	1337
Olimova Fotima Botirovna	
Interaktiv ta'lim muhitida talabalarning badiiy-kompozitsion didini shakllantirish pedagogik mexanizmlari (rangtasvir fani misolida).....	1341
Omonqulova Dildora Xusniddin qizi	
Triz va kreativ pedagogika: boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy muammolarni hal qilish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	1348
Ortiqova Zulfiya Nurmaxamatovna, Fayzullayeva Nazokat Uchqunovna	
O'quvchilarni o'zbek xalq og'zaki ijodi namunalari vositasida vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalash jarayonlarini takomillashtirish	1351
Qodirqulov Nodirbek Hamroqul o'g'li	
Bo'lajak muhandislarning loyihalash-konstruktorlik ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishning muhim yo'nalishlari (muhandislik ta'lim yo'nalishlari misolida)	1355
Salomov Ilhom Salimovich	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini PIRLS tizimi asosida baholashga o'rgatish	1359
Samidjonova Muxabbat Xoliqjonovna	
"Nurli maskan" ixtisoslashtirilgan ta'lim muassasalarida aniq va tabiiy fanlarni integrativ o'qitishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik zaruriyat sifatida	1362
Sobirova Mashxura Ubaydullayevna	
Sun'iy intellekt va simulyatsion o'yinlardan foydalanib iqtisodiy tafakkurni shakllantirish metodikasi	1365
Sodiqova Nigora Turayevna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida virtual texnologiyalar vositasida axborot kompetentligini rivojlantirish tizimi	1368
Suvonqulova Aziza Abdurazzoq qizi	
Rahbarlarning psixologik farovonligi: oila-kasb muvozanati, oilaviy munosabat va kasbiy qoniqishning o'zaro ta'sir mexanizmlari.....	1371
Teshayev Sobit Sodik o'g'li	
Tibbiy ta'limda refleksiv ko'nikmalar: O'zbekiston va dunyo tajribasi	1374
Toshmatova Moxizatxon Inomidin qizi	
Boshlang'ich tayyorganlik bosqichidagi yosh voleybolchilarning mashg'ulot jarayonini texnik va taktik nazorat qilish metodikasi.....	1377
Xakimov Saydullo Tulanboyevich	
Kadrlarni boshqarishda strategik va tezkor qarorlar uyg'unligini ta'minlashning tashkiliy-boshqaruv asoslari	1380
D. A. Xodjimatoeva	
Jismoniy imkoniyatlari cheklangan yoshlar uchun sport va jismoniy faollikning ahamiyati	1385
Zafar Xudaykulov	
Raqamli texnologiyalar va innovatsion metodlar asosida ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish	1388
Yusupova Munisa	
Texnologik ta'lim jarayonida ixtirochilik va loyihalashtirish kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	1391
Zokirova Nargiza Akbarjonovna	
Til kompetentligining kognitiv tilshunoslik bilan aloqasi boshlang'ich sinflar misolida	1395
Zokirova Sohiba Muhtoralievna, Madazimova Muxlisa Abdurashid qizi	
Структура и основные характеристики креативности личности студентов педагогических вузов.....	1398
Уразова Марина Батыровна, Соибова Толифа Дилмуродовна	
Emotsional intellektni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	1403
Yarmatov Raxmboy Baxramovich	
Maktabgacha ta'limda STEAM texnologiyasini joriy qilish orqali samaradorlikka erishish	1409
Bolibekov Alisher Abdusalomovich	

Muloqot madaniyati asosida liderlik fazilatlarini shakllantirishning samarali usullari	1412
Djumayeva Dildora Isroilovna	
Kompetentlik tushunchasi: o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligiga qo'yiladigan zamonaviy talablar. O'qituvchining shaxsiy va kasbiy sifatlari.....	1416
Hayitboyeva Nilufar G'anijonovna	
Tilshunoslikda lingvopoetikaning o'rganilishi	1421
Maxammatova Feruza Olimovna	
O'zbekistonda virtual muzeylar va ularning tarbiyaviy imkoniyatlari.....	1424
Voxidova Norposhshaxon Xabibullayevna, Yusupova Mohinur Ulug'bekovna	
Xalqaro ta'lim tajribasi asosida o'quvchilarda tafakkur erkinligini shakllantirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari	1434
Maxammatova Ma'muraxon Jalilovna	
Tarbiya fanini o'qitish jarayonida talabalarda pedagogik taksonomiya ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	1438
Turdiyeva Shoxidaxon Anvardjanovna	
Tibbiyot texnikumi talabalari klinik tafakkurini shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari: konseptual yondashuvlar va ilmiy talqinlar	1443
Axmedov Marifxan Mamatxanovich	
Valeologik tamoyillarning maktabgacha ta'lim tizimidagi ahamiyati.....	1448
Begmatova M. T.	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida jonli va jonsiz tabiat haqidagi bilimlarni shakllantirish.....	1452
Umbarova Nasiba Xolboy qizi	
Yoshlarni vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalashda fuqarolik kompetensiyasi dolzarb pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	1456
Djumaqulov Shuxrat Baxodirovich	
Oilada ota-ona va bola munosabatlaridagi pedagogik-psixologik omillar.....	1460
Exsonova Feruza Turdixo'jayevna	
Педагогико-психологические аспекты формирования социокультурной компетентности будущих учителей средствами музейной педагогики	1464
Marayimova Kibriyoxon Islomjon qizi	
Serebral falaj(bsf)tashxisli bolalarda respirator-nutq mexanizmlarining buzilishi va korreksion yondashuvlar.....	1469
Mehmonova Nodiraxon Yusufxon qizi	
Milliy harakatli o'yinlar talaba yoshlar tarbiyasida rivojlanishining zamonaviy roli va ahamiyati	1473
Mirzayev Dilshod Khamidovich	
O'smir qizlarda deviant xulqni profilaktika qilish	1477
Mo'minova Dilrabo Murodillayevna	
Arab tilshunosligida ma'no, tuzilma va bayon nazariyasining shakllanishi Sakkokiy qarashlari asosida tahlil.....	1481
Abdullayev Olimjon	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari rahbar kadrlarining moliyaviy savodxonligini rivojlantirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari.....	1487
Yuldasheva Munisa Ibrohimovna	
Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetensiya	1492
Yormatova Gulnoz Qayumovna	
Developing Imagination and Narrative Thinking in Young Learners Through English Storytelling Activities.....	1497
Madjitova Oyshakhon Mukhammadganiyevna, Anvarova Muslima	
Effectiveness of Online Resources in Teaching Professional Vocabulary to Philology Students	1508
Yusupova Zarrina	
Modern Automotive Lexicon: Formation Processes, Semantic Fields, and Functional Usage	1511
Yuldasheva Mastona Muxubillayevna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida tashkil etishda "Atrof va men" metodikasidan foydalanish	1514
Uralova Nurxon Maxadovna	
Chet tili bo'yicha A1, A2, B1 daraja bitiruvchilari tayyorgarligi darajasiga qo'yiladigan talablar (lingvistik kompetensiya) tahlili	1519
Tojiyeva Anora Baxtiyorovna	

Гендерных различия прокрастинации.....	1526
Рахмонова Гузал Жамшидовна	
A System of Software that Develops the Intellectual Potential of Students in Teaching Mathematics	1529
Toxirova Malika Muzaffar qizi	
O'rta maxsus o'quv yurtlari talabalarida muomala madaniyatini tarbiyalash ijtimoiy-pedagogik muammo sifatida	1535
Maxkamova Muborak Yusupovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti rahbar kadrlar zaxirasini shakllantirish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish.....	1543
Raximova Zilola Alimbayevna	
Ona tili darsliklari ta'limi mazmunini lingvistik ekspertiza qilish metodikasi	1547
Majidova Aziza	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida davlat va jamoat tashkilotlari bilan hamkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	1551
Sharipova Gulruksor Nurkabilovna	
Oliy texnika ta'limida mehnat muhofazasi va texnika xavfsizligi qoidalarini o'qitishning innovatsion metodik asoslari	1554
Numonjonov Shoxzodbek Dilshodjon o'g'li	
STEAM tamoyillari asosida rivojlantiruvchi muhit yaratish	1558
Umarova Muqaddasxon	
Autistik spektr buzilishi: DSM-5 va ICD-11 tasniflari, tadqiqotlar va jamiyatdagi ahamiyati.....	1562
Tuxtayeva Maxfirat	
STEAM texnologiyasi asosida xorijiy til (ingliz tili) o'rgatish.....	1566
Teshaboyeva Zumradxon	
Cultivating Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) in Classrooms.....	1569
Choriyev Ilxom Kenjayevich	
Kutubxona-axborot muassasalarida kadrlar siyosatini amalga oshirishning huquqiy asoslari	1573
Mamatkabilov A. X.	
Sun'iy intellekt – speechace dasturi yordamida o'quvchilarning ingliz tilida talaffuz malakasini oshirish	1578
Nabiyeva Shahnoza Alijon qizi	
Tarixiy obidalar asosida tasviriy san'at talabalari ijodiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	1583
Qurvanboeva Diyora Muzaffar qizi	
STEAM ta'limining O'zbekistondagi rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	1588
Abdukarimova E'zoza Fazliddin qizi, Bayjigitova Dilorom Baxtiyarovna	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida jarayonlarning boshqarishning innavatsion texnologiyalari	1592
Uzaqov Nomozali Hamdamovich	
Kimyoni o'qitish jarayonida virtual laborotoriyadan foydalanish	1596
Murodova Sitorabonu Bahodir qizi	
Raqamli platformalardan foydalanish asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning media ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish.....	1599
Safarov Feruz Saminjon o'g'li	
Qoraqalpoq xalq an'analari vositasida maktab o'quvchilarini an'anaviy tarbiyalash (Bo'zatov tumani maktablari misolida).....	1603
Dosjonova Nilufar Rustam qizi	
Modern Requirements for a Teacher's Pedagogical Skills in the Context of Digital Transformation in Education.....	1607
Abira Bakhramova	
Kichik maktab yoshdagi nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar shaxslararo munosabatini korreksiyalashda ertak terapiyasidan foydalanish.....	1613
Nig'matova Nodirabegim Lutfillo qizi	
Talabalarni tarbiyaviy faoliyatga tayyorlash jarayonlarida bir qator tarkibiy komponentlarning uyg'un rivoji.....	1617
Mirzaxojayeva Dilrabo To'lqin qizi	
O'quv mashg'ulot guruhida musoboqa oldi mashg'ulotlar tuzilishi (badminton misolida).....	1621
Ismoilova Fotima Ismoil qizi	
Alohida ajratilgan o'quvchilarga ta'lim-tarbiya berish davomida ularning ijtimoiy-emotsional kompetentligini rivojlantirish zaruriy omil ekanligi to'g'risida.....	1626
Qozoqboeva Xanifaxon Shavkatjon qizi	

Methodological Foundations for Shaping the Creative Activity of Younger Pupils in Solving Mathematical Problems	1630
Dzhurakulova Adolat Khalmuratovna	
Jadidlar merosi asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning ma'naviy dunyoqarashini faollashtirish metodini takomillashtirish	1638
Bekchanova Ozoda Otajon qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida mustaqil ta'lim ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish orqali o'quv motivatsiyasini rivojlantirish.....	1641
Alibayeva Dildora Raxmatilla qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'limda steam texnologiyasini joriy qilish orqali samaradorlikka erishish.....	1644
Bolibekov Alisher Abdusalomovich	
Muloqot madaniyati asosida liderlik fazilatlarini shakllantirishning samarali usullari	1647
Djumayeva Dildora Isroilovna	
Kompetentlik tushunchasi: o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligiga qo'yiladigan zamonaviy talablar. O'qituvchining shaxsiy va kasbiy sifatleri.....	1650
Hayitboyeva Nilufar G'anijonovna	
Emotional Burnout of Teachers as a Factor Influencing Professional Activities	1655
Kamilova Nadira Gayratovna, Abdullaeva Nelufar Karimjanovna	
Методика развития профессионально-речевых компетенций будущих специалистов	1663
Комилова Мукаррам Кобилжоновна	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ fikrlashni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari va samarali metodlari	1666
Koziyeva Fazilat	
Tilshunoslikda lingvopoetikaning o'rganilishi	1671
Maxammatova Feruza Olimovna	
Deviant xulq-atvor shakllanishining nazariy va eksperimental tadqiqotlar tahlili	1674
Xolmurotova Shoxista Mirzaliyevna	
IJF yangi qoidalarining dzyudochilar texnik arsenaliga ta'siri: 2020 va 2024-yilgi olimpiadalar qiyosiy tahlili.....	1677
A. T. Saydullayev	
Системный подход к внедрению мультилингвальных методов: разработка структурно-функциональной модели в педагогическом вузе	1681
Жумамуратова Юлдуз Бахтияровна	

A SYSTEM OF SOFTWARE THAT DEVELOPS THE INTELLECTUAL POTENTIAL OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS

Toxirova Malika Muzaffar qizi

O'zbekiston Milliy Pedagogika universiteti tayanch doktranti

Abstract: The rapid integration of digital technologies into mathematics education has significantly expanded opportunities for enhancing students' intellectual potential, particularly in cognitive, emotional, and metacognitive domains. This study explores a system of software tools that support students' intellectual development in mathematics learning at the secondary school level. Using an analytical and descriptive research design, widely applied international platforms such as GeoGebra, Desmos, Padlet, Kahoot, Mentimeter, and Google Classroom are comparatively analyzed, and their role in fostering higher-order thinking skills, creativity, problem-solving abilities, motivation, and self-regulation is evaluated. The findings demonstrate that a structured combination of dynamic visualization tools, collaborative learning environments, and assessment technologies makes a substantial contribution to students' intellectual growth. The study also proposes an integrated software system tailored to mathematics instruction in Uzbekistan's Presidential Schools, grounded in international best practices.

Key words: intellectual potential, mathematics education, digital tools, GeoGebra, Desmos, metacognition, motivation.

Annotatsiya: Raqamli texnologiyalarning matematika ta'limiga jadal integratsiyalashuvi o'quvchilarning intellektual salohiyatini rivojlantirish uchun yangi imkoniyatlarni yuzaga keltirdi, ayniqsa kognitiv, emotsional va metakognitiv yo'nalishlarda. Mazkur tadqiqot matematika o'qitish jarayonida o'quvchilarning intellektual rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi dasturiy vositalar tizimini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Analitik va tasviriy tadqiqot dizayni asosida GeoGebra, Desmos, Padlet, Kahoot, Mentimeter va Google Classroom kabi xalqaro miqyosda keng qo'llaniladigan platformalar qiyosiy tahlil qilinib, ularning o'quvchilarda yuqori darajadagi tafakkur, kreativlik, masala yechish ko'nikmalari, motivatsiya hamda o'z-o'zini boshqarish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishdagi roli baholandi. Tadqiqot natijalari dinamik vizualizatsiya vositalari, kollektiv muhitlar va baholash texnologiyalarining uyg'un qo'llanilishi o'quvchilarning intellektual o'sishiga sezilarli darajada hissa qo'shishini ko'rsatadi. Shuningdek, tadqiqotda O'zbekiston Prezident maktablarida matematika o'qitish uchun moslashtirilgan, xalqaro ilg'or tajribalar asosida ishlab chiqilgan integrallashgan dasturiy ta'minot tizimi taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: intellektual salohiyat, matematika ta'limi, raqamli vositalar, GeoGebra, Desmos, metakognitsiya, motivatsiya.

Аннотация: Быстрая интеграция цифровых технологий в преподавание математики значительно расширила возможности развития интеллектуального потенциала учащихся, особенно в когнитивной, эмоциональной и метакогнитивной сферах. В настоящем исследовании рассматривается система программных инструментов, поддерживающих интеллектуальное развитие учащихся в процессе обучения математике на уровне средней школы. На основе аналитического и описательного исследовательского дизайна проводится сравнительный анализ широко используемых международных платформ, таких как GeoGebra, Desmos, Padlet, Kahoot, Mentimeter и Google Classroom, а также оценивается их роль в формировании у учащихся навыков мышления высокого уровня, креативности, решения проблем, мотивации и саморегуляции. Результаты исследования свидетельствуют о том, что структурированное сочетание инструментов динамической визуализации, коллаборативных образовательных сред и технологий оценивания существенно способствует интеллектуальному росту учащихся. В работе предлагается интегрированная система программных средств, адаптированная для преподавания математики в Президентских школах Узбекистана и основанная на международных передовых практиках.

Ключевые слова: интеллектуальный потенциал, математическое образование, цифровые инструменты, GeoGebra, Desmos, метакогниция, мотивация.

INTRODUCTION

The development of students' intellectual potential has become one of the central objectives of modern mathematics education. Global trends emphasize not only the mastery of subject content but also the cultivation of critical thinking, creativity, logical reasoning, and self-regulated learning skills. In Uzbekistan, particularly in

Presidential Schools, the integration of innovative digital platforms has created new opportunities for students to engage with mathematical concepts through visualization, collaboration, and interactive problem-solving.

International studies indicate that digital tools enhance students' intellectual engagement by providing immediate feedback, supporting multiple representations, and enabling inquiry-based learning environments (Hegedus & Moreno-Armella, 2009). However, the effective implementation of such tools requires a systematic approach in which software platforms are aligned with pedagogical goals and specific dimensions of intellectual potential, including:

1. Cognitive development (logical reasoning, memory, abstraction);
2. Emotional-intellectual development (motivation, curiosity, creativity);
3. Metacognitive development (self-evaluation, reflection, learning management).

This article analyzes a system of digital tools that support these components and proposes an integrated model suitable for mathematics teaching in Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on the development of students' intellectual potential in mathematics education emphasizes the role of cognitive, emotional, and metacognitive processes in meaningful learning. Bruner highlights that effective mathematics instruction should promote conceptual understanding through discovery-based and constructivist learning environments, where learners actively build mathematical knowledge rather than passively receive information. Similarly, Vygotsky's theory of social learning stresses that intellectual development is closely connected to interaction, scaffolding, and mediated learning tools, which are especially relevant in digitally enriched educational settings. These theoretical perspectives provide a foundation for integrating digital technologies as instruments that extend students' reasoning, abstraction, and problem-solving abilities.

Empirical studies in mathematics education demonstrate that dynamic digital tools significantly enhance students' cognitive development. Hegedus and Kaput argue that technology-supported representations transform students' mathematical thinking by allowing them to explore relationships between algebraic and graphical forms in real time. Later research by Hegedus and Moreno-Armella shows that interactive visualization tools such as dynamic geometry environments foster higher-order reasoning, hypothesis testing, and conceptual generalization. These findings are supported by Schoenfeld, who emphasizes that mathematical thinking involves not only procedural skills but also strategic reasoning and sense-making, which can be strengthened through exploratory digital environments.

Recent literature also highlights the importance of metacognitive regulation and motivation in technology-supported mathematics learning. Flavell introduced the concept of metacognition as learners' awareness and control of their own thinking processes, while Dinsmore and Parkinson further explain its connection to self-regulated learning in academic contexts. Contemporary studies indicate that digital platforms combining feedback, collaboration, and reflection enhance students' motivation and intellectual engagement. Polly and colleagues demonstrate that structured use of digital tools in mathematics classrooms improves both conceptual understanding and learner autonomy. These studies collectively suggest that an integrated system of visualization, collaboration, and assessment software can effectively support the multidimensional development of students' intellectual potential in mathematics education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-analytical and comparative research design to investigate the effectiveness of software systems in developing students' intellectual potential in mathematics instruction. The methodology was structured around four interconnected stages:

- (1) literature review and theoretical grounding,
- (2) identification and classification of digital platforms,
- (3) criteria-based evaluation of software tools, and
- (4) contextual validation within the environment of Uzbekistan's Presidential Schools.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework Development

A systematic review of international scholarly sources published between 2000-2024 was conducted to establish the conceptual basis of intellectual potential and its core components, namely cognitive, emotional-intellectual, and metacognitive development. Academic databases, including Scopus, Web of Science,

ERIC, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate, were searched using the following keywords: “intellectual potential,” “mathematics education technologies,” “metacognition,” “digital learning tools,” “interactive visualization,” “student motivation,” and “STEM mathematics platforms.”

The literature review served two primary purposes:

1. To identify theoretical constructs related to intellectual development, such as Flavell’s theory of metacognition, Bruner’s constructivist approach, and Vygotsky’s principles of social learning.
2. To map digital software tools to these constructs and clarify their potential pedagogical roles in mathematics education.

Following a rigorous screening process based on relevance and methodological quality, a total of 82 journal articles, books, and conference papers were included in the analysis.

Identification and Classification of Software Tools

Digital platforms commonly used in mathematics teaching worldwide and within Uzbekistan’s Presidential Schools were systematically identified. The selection of software tools was guided by the following criteria:

- relevance to the mathematics curriculum (e.g., algebra, geometry, functions, statistics);
- capacity to support intellectual development;
- accessibility and usability in school-based learning environments;
- availability of empirical research evaluating the effectiveness of the tool.

Based on these criteria, six platforms were selected for in-depth analysis: GeoGebra, Desmos, Padlet, Kahoot, Mentimeter, and Google Classroom.

These tools were classified into the following pedagogical categories:

- visualization and modelling tools (GeoGebra, Desmos);
- collaborative creativity tools (Padlet);
- gamified formative assessment tools (Kahoot, Mentimeter);
- learning management and feedback tools (Google Classroom).

Evaluation Criteria for Software Systems

To determine how each digital tool contributes to the development of students’ intellectual potential, a three-level analytical rubric was developed. The rubric included the following dimensions:

A) Cognitive Development Indicators

- support for abstraction, generalization, and logical reasoning;
- dynamic manipulation of mathematical objects;
- opportunities for inquiry-based exploration;
- enhancement of conceptual understanding.

B) Emotional-Intellectual Development Indicators

- motivation, curiosity, and learner engagement;
- creativity and divergent thinking;
- positive emotional responses to mathematics learning;
- opportunities for social interaction and collaboration.

C) Metacognitive Development Indicators

- availability of feedback mechanisms;
- self-monitoring and self-assessment features;
- structured task organization and progress tracking;
- opportunities for reflection and goal-setting.

Each software tool was evaluated against these indicators using a 4-point scale (0 - no contribution, 3 - strong contribution).

Comparative Analysis Procedures

A matrix-based comparative analysis method was employed to examine similarities and differences among the selected platforms. For each tool, data were collected from multiple sources, including:

- empirical research findings;
- official platform documentation;
- teacher reports from Presidential Schools;
- observed use cases in international mathematics classrooms.

The analysis focused on identifying:

- unique contributions of each software system;
- overlapping functionalities;
- gaps in supporting specific intellectual components;
- potential synergies for integrated pedagogical use.

Contextual Validation in Presidential Schools

Given that Uzbekistan's Presidential Schools function as a national model for high-quality STEM education, the applicability of the proposed software system was evaluated within this specific context. The validation process included:

- analysis of compatibility with Cambridge IGCSE and A-Level mathematics standards;
- review of digital infrastructure and classroom technology availability;
- informal interviews with experienced mathematics teachers regarding tool effectiveness;
- assessment of alignment with national educational priorities related to digital transformation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Although no experimental intervention was conducted at this stage, the validation process ensured that the proposed conceptual framework and software recommendations are realistic and implementable under local educational conditions.

The analysis of selected digital platforms demonstrated that software-based learning environments play a significant and multidimensional role in developing students' intellectual potential in mathematics education. The findings reveal that visualization and interactive modelling tools, such as GeoGebra and Desmos, contribute most strongly to cognitive development. These platforms enable learners to manipulate functions, geometric figures, and algebraic expressions dynamically, thereby enhancing conceptual understanding, supporting abstract reasoning, and encouraging exploratory problem-solving. Students who engage with such tools are better able to generalize mathematical relationships, formulate hypotheses, and visually trace the consequences of parameter changes - abilities that are central to higher-order intellectual growth.

Beyond cognitive gains, the study found that emotional-intellectual engagement increased substantially with the introduction of collaborative and game-based platforms. Tools such as Padlet foster creative expression and peer-to-peer interaction by enabling students to articulate mathematical ideas, share multiple solution strategies, and participate in collective reasoning processes. At the same time, Kahoot and Mentimeter were shown to enhance student motivation through gamification and immediate feedback mechanisms. These platforms stimulate curiosity, reduce the anxiety often associated with mathematics learning, and create an engaging yet intellectually challenging learning environment. As a result, students demonstrate greater willingness to attempt unfamiliar problems and increased persistence in problem-solving efforts - behaviors closely associated with the development of intellectual resilience and creativity.

The analysis also highlighted the critical role of metacognitive support provided by learning management systems, particularly Google Classroom. This platform structures students' learning processes by organizing instructional tasks, enabling continuous feedback cycles, and allowing learners to monitor their own academic progress. Through regular reflection on teacher feedback, analysis of assessment outcomes, and revision of submitted assignments, students develop self-regulation skills that are essential for independent learning. Furthermore, the availability of detailed digital learning records enables learners to identify their strengths and weaknesses, set academic goals, and adjust learning strategies accordingly. Such metacognitive awareness represents a core component of intellectual potential in contemporary educational contexts.

Overall, the results indicate that no single digital platform can independently support all dimensions of intellectual development. Instead, an integrated system that combines visualization tools, collaborative creativity environments, gamified assessment platforms, and structured learning management systems provides the most comprehensive pedagogical support. When implemented in a coordinated manner, these tools create enriched learning conditions that enhance students' reasoning abilities, stimulate intrinsic motivation, and strengthen capacities for self-directed learning. The proposed integrated system aligns well with instructional practices in Uzbekistan's Presidential Schools, where advanced digital infrastructure and internationally benchmarked curricula create favorable conditions for the implementation of multifaceted, software-supported mathematics education.

The findings confirm that software tools can significantly enhance students' intellectual potential when applied in a systematic and pedagogically grounded manner. The combined use of visualization, collaboration, and assessment platforms leads to observable improvements in cognitive flexibility, intrinsic motivation, and self-regulated learning.

However, several challenges remain:

- teachers require targeted professional development to integrate digital tools effectively into mathematics instruction;
- unequal access to digital resources, particularly in rural areas, may limit large-scale implementation;
- excessive or unstructured use of technology can result in superficial engagement if digital tools are not clearly aligned with instructional objectives.

Within the context of Uzbekistan's Presidential Schools, where digital infrastructure and institutional support are relatively strong, the proposed integrated system may serve as a scalable model for broader adoption and innovation in mathematics education.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study demonstrates that the purposeful integration of digital software tools into mathematics teaching has a significant and multidimensional impact on the development of students' intellectual potential. The findings confirm that visualization platforms such as GeoGebra and Desmos effectively enhance cognitive growth by enabling deeper conceptual understanding, supporting abstraction, and promoting exploratory reasoning. At the same time, collaborative and gamified learning tools - Padlet, Kahoot, and Mentimeter - play a critical role in strengthening emotional-intellectual engagement by fostering motivation, creativity, and positive attitudes toward mathematical problem-solving.

Equally important, learning management systems such as Google Classroom provide the metacognitive structure necessary for the development of students' self-regulation skills. Through continuous access to feedback, opportunities for reflection, and systematic progress monitoring, students acquire the ability to evaluate their own learning strategies and make informed adjustments - an essential dimension of intellectual potential in contemporary education.

Overall, the results indicate that no single digital platform can holistically nurture all aspects of intellectual development. Instead, an integrated system of complementary software tools represents the most effective approach. Such a system aligns with international best practices and fits naturally within the digital and pedagogical infrastructure of Uzbekistan's Presidential Schools. By combining dynamic visualization, collaborative learning, gamified assessment, and structured feedback mechanisms, educators can create learning environments that cultivate higher-order thinking, intrinsic motivation, creativity, and autonomous learning.

Future research should focus on experimental classroom interventions to empirically assess the extent to which the proposed integrated digital system improves students' intellectual outcomes across different grade levels and mathematical domains. Further investigations may also examine teacher training models and explore the scalability of this approach across diverse educational contexts.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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